

Supplementary Information 1

Carbon storage potential of wood and biochar in global urban building scenarios

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1. Region definition

Table S1 reports the 61 regions (R61) used in the model runs and their mapping onto the aggregated region definitions at the level of 12 regions (R12), 32 regions (R32) and 6 regions (R6) .

Table S1 Regions used in the MESSAGEix-Buildings model runs (R61) and their mapping onto aggregation at the level of 12 regions (R12) in the MESSAGE model, 32 regions (R32) in the SSP Database (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways) – Version 2 (R32), and 6 regions based on the IPCC AR6 WGII report (IPCC 2022) (Small Island States not included).

R61	R12 ¹	R32 ²	R6	Description and countries ³
C-EEU-BGR	EEU	R32EU12-M	Europe	Bulgaria
C-EEU-CZE	EEU	R32EU12-H	Europe	Czechia
C-EEU-EST	EEU	R32EU12-H	Europe	Estonia
C-EEU-HRV	EEU	R32EU12-H	Europe	Croatia
C-EEU-HUN	EEU	R32EU12-H	Europe	Hungary
C-EEU-LTU	EEU	R32EU12-M	Europe	Lithuania
C-EEU-LVA	EEU	R32EU12-M	Europe	Latvia
C-EEU-POL	EEU	R32EU12-H	Europe	Poland
C-EEU-ROU	EEU	R32EU12-M	Europe	Romania
C-EEU-SVK	EEU	R32EU12-H	Europe	Slovakia
C-EEU-SVN	EEU	R32EU12-H	Europe	Slovenia
C-WEU-AUT	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Austria
C-WEU-BEL	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Belgium
C-WEU-CHE	WEU	R32EFTA	Europe	Switzerland
C-WEU-CYP	WEU	R32EU12-H	Europe	Cyprus
C-WEU-DEU	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Germany
C-WEU-DNK	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Denmark
C-WEU-ESP	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Spain
C-WEU-FIN	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Finland
C-WEU-FRA	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	France
C-WEU-GBR	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	United Kingdom
C-WEU-GRC	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Greece
C-WEU-IRL	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Ireland
C-WEU-ISL	WEU	R32EFTA	Europe	Island

¹ Aggregation on the 12-region level based on the MESSAGE model regions: Sub-Saharan Africa (AFR), China (CHN), Central and Eastern Europe (EEU), Former Soviet Union (FSU), Latin America and the Caribbean (LAM), Middle East and North Africa (MEA), North America (NAM), Pacific OECD (PAO) Other Pacific Asia (PAS), Rest of Centrally Planned Asia (RCPA), South Asia (SAS), Western Europe (WEU). Please, refer to the following website for full region description: <https://docs.messageix.org/projects/models/en/latest/pkg-data/node.html#region-aggregation-r12>

² Aggregation on the 32-region level based on the SSP Database (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways) - Version 2.0. Please, refer to the following website for full region description: <https://tntcat.iiasa.ac.at/SspDb/dsd?Action=htmlpage&page=10#regiondefs>

³ The description and country names are aligned as much as possible to the definition of the aggregation on the 32 region level.

Table 1 (continues)

R61	R11	R32	R6	Description and countries
C-WEU-ITA	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Italy
C-WEU-LUX	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Luxembourg
C-WEU-MLT	WEU	R32EU12-H	Europe	Malta
C-WEU-NLD	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Netherlands
C-WEU-NOR	WEU	R32EFTA	Europe	Norway
C-WEU-PRT	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Portugal
C-WEU-SWE	WEU	R32EU15	Europe	Sweden
R32ANUZ	PAO	R32ANUZ	Australasia	Australia and New Zealand
R32BRA	LAM	R32BRA	South America	Brazil
R32CAN	NAM	R32CAN	North America	Canada
R32CAS-CAU	FSU	R32CAS	Asia	Central Asia – Caucasus region. Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia
R32CAS-OTH	FSU	R32CAS	Asia	Central Asia – Other regions. Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan
R32CHN	CHN	R32CHN	Asia	China
R32EEU	EEU	R32EEU	Europe	Eastern Europe (excl. former Soviet Union). Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Montenegro, Serbia, The former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia
R32EEU-FSU	FSU	R32EEU-FSU	Europe	Eastern Europe, former Soviet Union (excl. Russia). Belarus, Republic of Moldova, Ukraine
R32IDN	PAS	R32IDN	Asia	Indonesia
R32IND	SAS	R32IND	Asia	India
R32JPN	PAO	R32JPN	Asia	Japan
R32KOR	PAS	R32KOR	Asia	Republic of Korea
R32LAM-L	LAM	R32LAM-L	South America	Countries of Latin America (excl. Brazil, Mexico) - low income. Belize, Guatemala, Haiti, Honduras, Nicaragua
R32LAM-M	LAM	R32LAM-M	South America	Countries of Latin America (excl. Brazil, Mexico) - medium and high income. Antigua and Barbuda, Argentina, Bahamas, Barbados, Bermuda, Bolivia (Plurinational State of), Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Dominica, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, El Salvador, French Guiana, Grenada, Guadeloupe, Guyana, Jamaica, Martinique, Netherlands Antilles, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Saint Lucia, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Suriname, Trinidad and Tobago, Uruguay, Venezuela (Bolivarian Republic of)
R32MEA-H	MEA	R32MEA-H	Asia	Countries of Middle East Asia - high income. Bahrain, Israel, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates
R32MEA-M	MEA	R32MEA-M	Asia	This region includes the countries of Middle East Asia - low and medium income. Iran (Islamic Republic of), Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Occupied Palestinian Territory, Syrian Arab Republic, Yemen
R32MEX	LAM	R32MEX	South America	Mexico
R32NAF	MEA	R32NAF	Africa	Countries of North Africa. Algeria, Egypt, Libyan Arab Jamahiriya, Morocco, Tunisia, Western Sahara
R32OAS-CPA	RCPA	R32OAS-CPA	Asia	Countries of Other Asia - former Centrally Planned Asia. Cambodia, Lao People's Democratic Republic, Mongolia, Viet Nam
R32OAS-L-PAS	PAS	R32OAS-L	Asia	Countries of Other Asia part of the PAS region - low income. Democratic People's Republic of Korea, Fiji, Micronesia (Fed. States of), Myanmar, Papua New Guinea, Philippines, Samoa, Solomon Islands, Timor-Leste, Tonga, Vanuatu

Table 1 (continues)

R61	R11	R32	R6	Description and countries
R32OAS-L-SAS	SAS	R32OAS-L	Asia	Countries of Other Asia part of the SAS region - low income. Bangladesh and Nepal
R32OAS-M-PAS	PAS	R32OAS-M	Asia	Countries of Other Asia part of the SAS region - medium and high income. Brunei Darussalam, French Polynesia, Guam, Malaysia, New Caledonia, Singapore, Thailand
R32OAS-M-SAS	SAS	R32OAS-M	Asia	Countries of Other Asia part of the SAS region - medium and high income. Bhutan, Maldives, Sri Lanka
R32PAK	SAS	R32PAK	Asia	Pakistan and Afghanistan
R32RUS	FSU	R32RUS	Asia	Russian Federation
R32SAF	AFR	R32SAF	Africa	South Africa
R32SSA-L	AFR	R32SSA-L	Africa	Countries of Sub-Saharan Africa (excl. South Africa) - low income. Benin, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cameroon, Cape Verde, Central African Republic, Chad, Comoros, Congo, Côte d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Djibouti, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mozambique, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Sao Tome and Principe, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Sudan, Sudan, Swaziland, Togo, Uganda, United Republic of Tanzania, Zambia, Zimbabwe
R32SSA-M	AFR	R32SSA-M	Africa	Countries of Subsaharan Africa (excl. South Africa) - medium and high income. Angola, Botswana, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Mauritius, Mayotte, Namibia, Réunion, Seychelles
R32TUR	WEU	R32TUR	Europe	Turkey
R32USA	NAM	R32USA	North America	United States of America

2. Model implementation

Table S2 reports an overview of the main model dimensions and related parameter settings.

Table S2 Model dimensions and related parameter settings in the global implementation of the model, based on (Mastrucci et al 2021, 2024, Mastrucci and Ruijven 2023)

Dimension	Values	Dependent parameter setting
Country ⁴	174 countries	Population, Urbanization, GDP
Regions	61 regions (R61)	Floorspace per capita, building type
	32 regions (R32)	Material intensity
	12 regions (R12)	Embodied emission factors
Location	Urban	Floorspace per capita, building types
Building type	Single Family House (SFH), Multi-Family House (MFH), Commercial.	Floorspace per capita, material intensity

⁴ Data further aggregated from country level to MESSAGEix-Buildings model regions (R61).

3. Input data

The main model parameters and data sources used in this study are reported in Table S3. Data inputs not reported in this section are based on the implementation for the Shared Socioeconomic Pathway SSP2 in prior studies (Mastrucci *et al* 2021, Mastrucci and Ruijven 2023).

Table S3 Overview of model parameters and data sources, revised and updated from (Mastrucci *et al* 2021).

Category	Parameter	Unit	Resolution	Main data sources used*
Demographics and socio-economics	Population	million	Country	Database (IIASA 2024, KC <i>et al</i> 2023)
	Urbanization	%	Country	Database (IIASA 2024)
	Household size	number of members	Country	Database (UN 2019)
	GDP	\$2005PPP/cap	Country	Database (IIASA 2024)
Residential buildings	Share of SFH/MFH	%	Region, Location	Household survey data*, literature (Mastrucci <i>et al</i> 2021)
	Floorspace per capita	m ² /cap	Country, Location, Housing type	Household survey data*, literature (Fishman <i>et al</i> 2021, Harvey 2014, Mastrucci <i>et al</i> 2021)
	Building lifetime	years	Region, Housing type	Literature (Deetman <i>et al</i> 2020, Marinova <i>et al</i> 2020)
Commercial buildings	Floorspace per capita	m ² /cap	Region	Literature (Harvey 2014)
	Building lifetime	years	Region	Literature (Deetman <i>et al</i> 2020, Marinova <i>et al</i> 2020)
Materials	Material intensity		Region, Building type, Material	Literature (Berrill and Hertwich 2021, Dodoo <i>et al</i> 2014, Fishman <i>et al</i> 2024)
Emissions	Embodied emission factors	kgCO ₂ /kg	Region, Material	Literature (Zhong <i>et al</i> 2021); databases (Wernet <i>et al</i> 2016).
	Carbon storage potential	kgCO ₂ /kg	Material	Literature (Rüter <i>et al</i> 2019, Zhou <i>et al</i> 2026),

Note: * A complete description of the survey data used for different countries and world regions is available in prior publications (Mastrucci *et al* 2021).

3.1. Material intensities

We represent the material composition of different building types using region-specific material intensity coefficients from previous studies (Fishman *et al* 2024). We report the regional average material intensities in the base year by building type and material in Table S5.

Region	Building type	Aluminum	Brick	Concrete	Copper	Glass	Steel	Wood
Africa	Residential - SFH	0.49	645.35	566.00	0.18	5.79	17.30	38.89
Africa	Residential - MFH	0.49	212.59	965.15	0.18	2.47	50.80	19.20
Africa	Commercial	0.49	206.50	1078.61	0.18	2.00	54.68	19.29
Asia	Residential - SFH	0.49	473.62	584.42	0.18	3.23	20.66	37.60
Asia	Residential - MFH	0.49	215.64	1032.01	0.18	2.28	47.76	20.63
Asia	Commercial	0.49	245.48	1068.06	0.18	2.07	60.77	12.57
Australasia	Residential - SFH	0.49	132.80	169.26	0.19	3.36	6.44	68.39
Australasia	Residential - MFH	0.49	253.14	937.52	0.18	3.03	49.65	22.01
Australasia	Commercial	0.49	148.47	1070.52	0.18	2.57	47.16	25.62
Europe	Residential - SFH	0.49	691.92	616.24	0.18	3.94	22.31	30.75
Europe	Residential - MFH	0.49	261.08	946.24	0.18	3.03	52.60	15.53
Europe	Commercial	0.50	112.82	1086.11	0.19	2.82	45.59	25.63
North America	Residential - SFH	0.49	578.84	483.15	0.18	5.94	8.79	46.11
North America	Residential - MFH	0.49	226.96	850.64	0.18	3.14	39.70	33.97
North America	Commercial	0.49	148.47	1053.22	0.18	2.57	49.95	25.28
South America	Residential - SFH	0.49	640.00	566.00	0.18	5.79	30.50	39.27
South America	Residential - MFH	0.49	234.00	949.36	0.18	2.20	49.00	19.44
South America	Commercial	0.49	206.50	1088.71	0.18	2.00	54.68	19.29

For wood-based structures in the Wood scenario, we identify a specific set of material intensity coefficients for concrete, steel, and wood (Table S5). Values for different building types are from the literature. We assume cross-laminated timber (CLT) construction for multi-family housing and commercial buildings (Dodoo *et al* 2014)

Table S5 Material intensity coefficients for wood construction in the Wood scenario.

Building type	Reference	Concrete	Steel	Wood
Single-family house	(Berrill and Hertwich 2021)	111.9	5.9	72.3
Multi-family house and commercial buildings	(Dodoo <i>et al</i> 2014)	108.7	4.7	122.5

4. Sensitivity analyses

4.1. Carbon storage potential of construction materials

We run sensitivity analysis by varying the carbon storage potential of structural wood and biochar-based concrete within the ranges in the literature (Table S6). For biochar-based concrete, we assumed a reference conservative biochar content in cement of 2.5% to ensure structural resistance (Zhao *et al* 2024), resulting in a carbon storage potential of 0.011 kg/kg. In the sensitivity analysis, we vary biochar content in cement between 0.5% and 5.0%, representing a range emerging from current literature (Zhao *et al* 2024). For wood, we assume as reference the carbon storage potential of 1.833 (Rüter *et al* 2019), which is central in the range provided in existing literature (Van Roijen *et al* 2025). The results of the sensitivity analysis are reported in Figure 2a in the main text.

Table S6 Ranges of carbon storage potential in the sensitivity analysis for biochar-based concrete and structural wood.

Material	Carbon storage potential (kgCO ₂ /kg)			Sources
	Minimum	Reference	Maximum	
Biochar-based concrete	0.002	0.011	0.022	(Zhao <i>et al</i> 2024)
Structural wood	1.47	1.833	2.20	(Rüter <i>et al</i> 2019, Van Roijen <i>et al</i> 2025)

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